

Efficient RSS-Based DoA Estimation for ESPAR Antennas Using Multiplane SDR Calibration Approach

Mateusz Groth, Luiza Leszkowska, and Lukasz Kulas

(1) Department of Microwave and Antenna Engineering, Faculty of Electronics, Telecommunications and Informatics, Gdansk University of Technology, Poland; e-mail: {mateusz.groth, luiza.leszkowska, lukasz.kulas}@eti.pg.gda.pl

Direction-of-Arrival (DoA) estimation is a technique that can be used to improve key parameters of modern wireless systems, including connectivity, coverage and energy efficiency. In its most common implementation, it relies on digital beamforming and requires a number of digital signal processing (DSP) units, which has a negative impact on total system cost and energy consumption [1]. To address these deficiencies, one can use simpler and more energy efficient electronically steerable parasitic array radiator (ESPAR) antenna concept, first proposed in [2], in which a centrally placed active element is surrounded by a number of passive elements that are connected to variable reactances. By setting up the correct values of reactances, one can form a directional main beam, and by changing these values electronically it is possible to rotate the main beam around the antenna.

ESPAR antenna has been used by many authors to estimate the direction of a signal impinging the antenna [3]-[5]. One of the most practical approach relies on power-pattern cross-correlation (PPCC) algorithm that uses received signal strength (RSS) values recorded at the antenna output for different main beam directions. By comparing the recorded RSS values with antenna's radiation patterns measured in an anechoic chamber during the calibration phase, it is possible to estimate DoA with 2° precision [4]. However, in its original implementation PPCC-based DoA estimation may cause errors when elevation angle of an unknown incoming signal is different than $\theta = 90^\circ$, as in the calibration procedure ESPAR antenna radiation patterns are measured only in the horizontal plane (i.e. for $\theta = 90^\circ$) [6]. It means that in many practical scenarios, in which a wireless module is placed higher than the ESPAR antenna performing measurements, DoA estimation results may be not be as accurate as for $\theta = 90^\circ$.

To improve PPCC estimator so it can provide accurate DoA estimation results for arbitrary elevation angles, a two-step approach has been proposed [6]. In the modified PPCC algorithm two calibration planes (i.e. $\theta_{90} = 90^\circ$ and $\theta_{45} = 45^\circ$) are used and then two PPCC estimators are calculated. By choosing the estimator providing the biggest value it was possible to increase the overall PPCC-based DoA estimation performance for arbitrary elevation angles. Because such an approach provides acceptable results only when a signal impinging the antenna comes from elevation angles between $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $\theta = 50^\circ$, further extension has been proposed involving a new PPCC estimator involving multiplane calibration [7], so the number of calibration planes can easily be extended to provide acceptable accuracy level. As result presented in [7] indicate, by increasing the number of calibration planes it is possible to increase the overall DoA estimation accuracy in a wide span of elevation angles. One has to note, however, that every additional calibration plane added to the PPCC estimator increases also the associated calculation time required for DoA estimation.

In this article, we propose to generate calibration measurements using software-defined radio (SDR) setup and then include them gradually within the PPCC estimator in an iterative manner by covering angles with the highest DoA estimation errors. To verify the proposed method we have applied it to the ESPAR antenna presented in Fig. 1. We have installed the antenna in our $11.9 \times 5.6 \times 6.0$ m anechoic chamber and have measured its radiation patterns at 2.484 GHz with horizontal and vertical resolution equal to 1° using an SDR-based device NI PXIe-5840 and using 100 sinusoidal snapshots for each measurement. Because the device can act as a signal generator and a signal analyzer, NI PXIe-5840 has also been used to verify DoA estimation accuracy. To this end, in the same anechoic chamber 10 snapshots of 10 dBm 2.484 GHz BPSK test signal were generated 8.0 m from the ESPAR antenna for every RSS measurement. All signals have been received by the same NI PXIe-5840 unit connected to ESPAR antenna's output and then additive white Gaussian noise has been added to obtain signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) equal to 20 dB. To provide accurate test results, signal's directions were set by rotating the receiving ESPAR antenna with a discrete angular step equal to 5° in both θ and φ directions. It means that 72 test directions $\varphi_t \in \{0^\circ, 5^\circ, \dots, 355^\circ\}$ were set up for 17 elevation angles $\theta_t \in \{90^\circ, 85^\circ, \dots, 15^\circ, 10^\circ\}$. Additionally, for every 2D signal's direction (θ_t, φ_t) twelve RSS values have been recorded for all the main beam antenna configurations.

Fig. 1. The fabricated ESPAR antenna together with numbering of its parasitic elements.

For multiplane calibration approach with $M = 9$ calibration planes set up at $\{\theta_1 = 10^\circ, \theta_2 = 20^\circ, \dots, \theta_9 = 90^\circ\}$ as proposed in [7], the overall root-mean-square (RMS) error calculated from all 1224 error values equals 19.20° . This is caused mainly by considerable errors at $\theta_t = 15^\circ$, not visible when coarse angular step is used for testing as in [7]. By applying the proposed iterative approach, we first had set up only two calibration planes, namely $\{\theta_1 = 10^\circ, \theta_2 = 90^\circ\}$, which resulted in the total RMS error equal 59.66° and with the highest RMS error value at the vertical angle $\theta_t = 40^\circ$. Then, we inserted an additional plane ($\theta_3 = 40^\circ$) within the PPCC estimator, which resulted in the overall RMS error equal to 18.33° with the highest RMS error value at vertical angle $\theta_t = 15^\circ$. By inserting additional calibration plane ($\theta_4 = 15^\circ$) the overall RMS error dropped to 1.65° , which is a value acceptable in most of DoA applications. Therefore, with the proposed multiplane SDR-based approach, it is possible to obtain efficient PPCC-based DoA estimation that provides acceptable result using only $M = 4$ calibration planes that are now placed in more optimal manner than it was proposed in [7].

Research leading to these results has received funding from the EU ECSEL Joint Undertaking under grant agreement no. 737459 (project Productive4.0) and from the National Centre for Research and Development on behalf of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education in Poland.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Chandran, *Advances in Direction-of-Arrival Estimation*. London, U.K.: Artech House, 2005.

- [2] R. Harrington, "Reactively controlled directive arrays," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. AP-26, no. 3, pp. 390-395, May 1978.
- [3] E. Taillefer, C. Plapous, J. Cheng, K. Iigusa, and T. Ohira, "Reactance-domain MUSIC for ESPAR antennas (experiment)," in *Proc. IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conf.*, vol. 1, New Orleans, LA, Mar. 2003, pp. 98–102.
- [4] E. Taillefer, A. Hirata, and T. Ohira, "Direction-of-arrival estimation using radiation power pattern with an ESPAR antenna," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 678–684, Feb. 2005.
- [5] L. Kulas, "RSS-based DoA Estimation Using ESPAR Antennas and Interpolated Radiation Patterns," *IEEE Antennas Wireless Propag. Lett.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 25-28, Jan 2018.
- [6] M. Rzymowski and L. Kulas, "RSS-Based Direction-of-Arrival Estimation with Increased Accuracy for Arbitrary Elevation Angles Using ESPAR Antennas," in *Proc. 12th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, 2017, (accepted for publication).
- [7] M. Groth and L. Kulas, "Accurate PPCC-Based DoA Estimation Using Multiple Calibration Planes for WSN Nodes Equipped with ESPAR Antennas," in *Proc. 48th Euro. Microw. Conf.*, Madrid, Spain, 2018, (in review).